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WHEATBIOME

**Unraveling the potential of the wheat microbiome for the
development of healthier, more sustainable and resilient
wheat-derived food & feed products**

DELIVERABLE D8.3

MID-PROJECT DATA MANAGEMENT

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Dissemination Level

PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
SEN	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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V0.3	28/06/2024	3 rd draft by project manager with revisions from partners
V0.4	12/07/2024	4 th draft by project manager with revisions from coordinators
V1.0	19/07/2024	Final version reviewed by coordinators

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Mid-project Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the comprehensive framework for handling all datasets collected and generated by the WheatBiome project between M1 and M18, detailing the consortium's revised data management policies. This updated version of the previous version of the DMP incorporates enhanced policies and procedures addressing both administrative and technical data management aspects. It elaborates on data and metadata collection, the publication and deposition of open data, and the infrastructure for data repositories, ensuring compliance with the Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE).

The mid-project DMP emphasizes the adherence of WheatBiome project to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) for data management. It reinforces the standards for data collection, processing, sharing, and preservation and provides detailed information on how the datasets are being collected, analyzed and stored. Additionally, it outlines improved guidelines for data curation to ensure long-term accessibility and usability of the WheatBiome datasets.

This version aims to enhance the clarity and effectiveness of the data management processes within the WheatBiome project, supporting the ongoing evolution and improvement of data practices and ensuring robust data stewardship throughout the project's lifecycle.

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3. ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

DMP – Data Management Plan

FAIR - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable

M- Month

OpenAIRE - Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe

WP – Work Package

4. DATA SUMMARY

The WheatBiome project will integrate re-used data from existing databases from past and ongoing national and European projects and from the literature (such as SCOPUS, Web of Science, PubMed, and ScienceDirect) with novel results generated within each work package (WP).

The project is expected to generate different types of data, including:

- Agricultural practices and crop management data
- General environmental and meteorological variables
- Quantitative and qualitative nutritional characterization datasets
- Laboratory experimental data
- DNA sequencing data
- Multiomics (proteomics and metabolomics) experimental data
- Sensory analysis data
- Health related (bioaccessibility, bioavailability of bioactive compounds and immunogenic proteins) and food quality properties (molecular analysis of taste)
- Food and feed fermentation data
- Consumer survey data
- Statistical and comparative analysis results
- Life Cycle Assessment and economic valuation data

The integration of reused data with novel data is expected to aid knowledge in understanding the entire food and feed production chain, from environmental conditions and agricultural practices to the nutritional quality and consumer acceptance of the final products:

- Environmental and agricultural data will inform best practices for crop management and sustainability (WP1 & WP2).
- Nutritional, food safety and quality datasets will help in characterizing and optimizing fermented wheat-based products (WP3).
- Data from cellular in vitro assays, consumer surveys and clinical trials will validate the health benefits and acceptance of these products (WP4).
- Feed product validation will ensure the safety and nutritional adequacy of novel feed formulations (WP5).
- Life Cycle Assessment and economic valuation data will evaluate the environmental and economic benefits of these innovations (WP6).

The data generated from month 1 (M1) to month 18 (M18) is related to the ongoing activities being performed among all working packages with the exception for WP4, which has not started yet. The data includes laboratory notebooks, text documents, spreadsheets (e.g., experimental procedures), database contents (large-scale data processing), documented methodologies, and workflows, among others.

Data is being organized and stored in standard file formats such as Excel spreadsheets (.xlsx), Word documents (.docx), text files (.txt), powerpoint slide presentations (pptx); vectorial designs (.ai, .svg); images (.png, .jpeg) and sequencing data files (.bam, .fastq, .fq.gz) mainly on institutional personal computers and shared clouds.

Between M1 to M18, WheatBiome produced mostly numerical datasets from experimental data recorded by field and laboratory equipment, and, to a lesser extent, datasets with text entries which is being collected mostly from the surveys.

The type and formats of data obtained for each WP are listed on table 1.

Table 1: Information about the type of data, format and storage produced within WheatBiome work packages in the first 18 months of project duration.

WP	Type of Data	Format	Storage
1	Sampling protocols and experimental designs; Experimental results from wheat quality and protein analysis from 2023 samples; Results from analyses of soil physical and chemical characteristics; Microbiome sequencing data; Proteomics analysis results;	.doc, .pdf, .xlsx, .pptx, .fq.gz, .raw	Notebooks; Institutional personal computers; Share clouds (institutional OneDrive, research group Dropbox and Teams platform)
2	Data from the surveys to food systems actors	.xlsx, .doc	Notebooks; Institutional personal computers; Teams share space for WP2
3	Data from experimental analysis (including indicators for key fermentation parameters and DNA	.raw, .log, .dat, xls, .doc	Notebooks; Institutional

	sequencing data of novel microorganisms) and protocols; Results of experimental analysis, data summaries, internal reports		personal computers; Teams share space for WP3
4	No data produced yet		
5	Data from analytical analysis of start cultures of novel microorganisms; Fermentation parameters for development of novel fermented feed products	.xlsx	Notebooks; Institutional personal computers; Teams share space for WP5
6	Data generated from Life Cycle Assessment and the Economic valuation: Information of life-cycle process diagrams, equipment used, operational parameters, material inputs and outputs, energy consumptions and costs, product compositions, emissions, workforce costs, equipment and material costs	.xlsx	Teams WP6 share space
7	Communication materials (brochures, posters, infographics, logos); Communication & Dissemination Plan; Communication guidelines; Slide presentations of WheatBiome; Practice abstracts	.docx, .pptx, .pdf, .jpeg	Institutional personal computers; Teams shared cloud storage for WP7
8	Deliverables; Data management reports; Ethical issues and guidelines Slide presentations for consortium meetings; Meeting minutes and agendas; Supporting figures; Contact list	.xlsx, .pptx, .pdf, .doc, .jpeg, .png	Institutional personal computers; Teams share space for WP8
9	Ethics requirements reports and deliverables	.doc, .pdf	Institutional personal computers; Teams share space for WP9

5. FAIR DATA

The data generated within the framework of WheatBiome will be made accessible, whenever possible, through open data repositories, ensuring compliance with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) to maximize its utility and impact among a wide range of stakeholders:

- Researchers and Scientists from agronomy, microbiology, nutrition, and environmental sciences, with an interest in the interactions between microbiomes and crop production.
- Agricultural Practitioners and Farmers aiming to improve sustainable agricultural practices and crop management techniques.
- Food and Feed Industry Professionals seeking new knowledge to develop and/or optimize new products with enhanced nutritional profiles and sustainability credentials.
- Policy Makers and Regulators that are enrolled into the guidelines and policies related to sustainable agriculture, food safety, and environmental protection.
- Consumers and Consumer Advocacy Groups focused on understanding the nutritional benefits and safety of new food products.
- Educational Institutions aiming to improve their curricular teaching and training related to agriculture, food science, and sustainability.

The results obtained between M1 and M18 are mostly preliminary, and they are being processed and analysed for further dissemination through publications on open repositories and dissemination activities.

5.1. MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

As defined in the first version of DMP (Deliverable D8.2), the WheatBiome project is following the Dublin Core Schema for standardizing metadata, which is adopted by the Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE) to ensure that research outputs are easily findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable.

WheatBiome Community was already created in Zenodo platform (<https://zenodo.org/communities/wheatbiome>), and it will be used to deposit project outputs, including datasets and corresponding descriptive information (metadata). The communication manager will add the metadata manually when uploading the datasets in Zenodo repository, including authors information (ORCID iD), date of creation, format,

methodology and source of dataset. Additionally, specific keywords will also be manually added to each dataset to optimize its trackability and potential reuse by others.

Zenodo attributes a persistent identifier, such as Digital Object Identifiers (DOI), to each upload, making the content easily identifiable. Moreover, Zenodo allows users to connect the content to author's ORCID iD; this integration ensures that the work is correctly attributed to the right researcher and discoverability of research outputs is improved. By linking the WheatBiome community with the Research Organization Registry ID (a global repository with unique persistent identifiers for research organizations) (Fig. 1) the community can be easily found, promoting greater transparency and collaboration among partners institutions beyond the consortium.

Figure 1: The WheatBiome community in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/wheatbiome/>).

5.2. MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE

The WheatBiome project is committed to making its data accessible to the wider research community and stakeholders, following the principles of Open Science. Preliminary data produced and collected in the first 18 months of WheatBiome project is stored and shared on the WheatBiome Teams platform, an effective tool for collaborative work hosted by the coordinating institution, as outlined in the Project Management Plan (deliverable 8.1).

All datasets that are not sensitive or restricted is being processed for deposition in reputable open access repositories, such as Zenodo.

Open access datasets will be announced on the WheatBiome project website (<https://www.wheatbiome-project.eu/>) with a direct link to Zenodo, enhancing data and metadata dissemination and accessibility.

Final data will be shared under open licenses (e.g., Creative Commons licenses) that will allow free use, distribution, and reproduction, provided proper attribution is given to the WHEATBIOME project. Clear guidelines on the permissible use of the data will ensure that users understand the terms under which they can access and use the datasets.

5.3. MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

To make data interoperable, WheatBiome is using terms and units in agreement with the international scientific community and International System of Units, respectively.

The vast majority of the datasets are being stored under common and standard formats (eg. .xlsx, .doc or .txt file formats) so that they can be easily accessed by future potential users.

5.4. MAKING DATA RE-USE

To ensure the reusability of data generated within the WheatBiome project, each dataset is accompanied by detailed documentation outlining its context, methodology, limitations, and potential applications, enhancing its usability for future researchers. Additionally, relevant contextual information, such as research objectives, experimental designs, and data collection protocols, will be further provided to aid in understanding and interpreting the published data.

As described above, datasets with non-sensitive information will be shared following Open Science premises, allowing for unrestricted reuse and redistribution under CC0 license (<https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/>). For sensitive datasets, controlled access will be established to manage access requests while still facilitating reuse by authorized users, ensuring compliance with ethical and legal requirements. Clear guidelines for data citation will be provided to ensure proper attribution of the datasets in publications and research outputs, promoting transparency and recognition of contributors.

These efforts aim to foster a culture of open science and data sharing within the WheatBiome project, maximizing the potential for collaboration, innovation, and knowledge advancement in the field of wheat research and novel food development.

6. OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS

In addition to the data management, WheatBiome will also manage other research outputs generated within the work plan of the project, which will be shared under FAIR principles. For instance, WP3 is planning to create new protocols for development of new beverages based on the strains incorporated in the new wheat-based products. These protocols will be shared in Zenodo. Moreover, a new digital decision support tool will be developed within the framework of WP2. Due to the lack of information at the present, further details about

digital and/or physical research outputs will be included on the final data management plan (Deliverable 8.4).

7. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

At the present, there are no costs associated with implementing mechanisms to make the database FAIR and ensure long-term preservation. Zenodo, which will be used to deposit most of the open access data produced within the WheatBiome, is a free repository with no costs associated. The communication manager (from CONTACTICA) and the project manager (from REQUIMTE, the coordinating institution) will oversee the quality assurance of data files and handle their submission in Zenodo.

Since WheatBiome is committed to openly publishing research outputs, resources were allocated on the project budget to support open-access publications.

Ultimately, the project coordinators bear the overarching responsibility for data management throughout the project lifecycle.

8. DATA SECURITY

The majority of data generated as project output is being stored on the Teams platform, hosted by the coordinating institution integrated in the University of Porto. The security of data is upheld by the institution's IT infrastructure, ensuring compliance with confidentiality and data protection regulations.

Data collected and stored on institutional personal computers are protected by multiple measures such as mono or multi-factor authentication step (password or biometric); security with up to date antivirus and malware software, firewalls and updated operating systems; access to security protocols implemented for institutional wireless or cable network and virtual private networks (VPN) for remote access; institutional in house security policies, including secure facilities with controlled entrance, particularly among the beneficiaries that are educational institutions.

Zenodo is hosted in CERN and employs several measures to ensure the security and integrity of the data uploaded by users, including secure communication protocols (such as HTTPS) to encrypt data during transfer between users, backup systems to ensure the availability and durability of data, regular data integrity checks to prevent data corruption

and the possibility to define the access level - publicly accessible, restricted access or private - for each content.

9. ETHICS

The ethical aspects related to the personal data and informed consent collected by WheatBiome team and stored in datasets is secured by an appointed external ethical advisor, who will report all ethical aspects and concerns in the deliverables associated with the work package 9 – Ethics requirements.